

EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING MANAGEMENT MODEL IN RANONG, THAILAND: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING APPROACH

YANANDA SIRAPHATTHADA¹, DUANGKAMOL THITIVESA² and PARICHART
RATTANABUNSAKUL³

^{1, 2, 3} Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Thailand. Email: yananda.si@ssru.ac.th¹, duangkamol.th@ssru.ac.th², parichart.th@ssru.ac.th³

Abstract

Different types of safety measures are very important for any organization so that the employees of the organization feel satisfied with their jobs. There are different behavioral and psychological aspects related to the safety culture. The basic objective of the study was to find out the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects, safety culture psychological aspects and use of mobile technology on employee well-being in the mediating role of safety at work. The data has been collected from 450 employees working in the herbal companies and Software program have been run on the collected data. The results of these tests show that the impact of the independent variables i.e. safety culture psychological aspects and use of mobile technology on employee well being is significant. But the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects has not been found as significant. In the similar way, the mediating impact of safety at work is significant in all cases i.e. between the relationship between all independent and dependent variables. The author has identified different theoretical, practical and policy making benefits of the study. Different limitations and future research indications in association with this study have also been discussed.

Keywords: Safety Culture, Mobile Technology, well-being, Thailand

1. INTRODUCTION

Safety culture practices can easily be promoted through the acquisition of the knowledge about safety and its practical implications (Berumen-Flucker et al., 2019; Charalambous & Kelly, 2018; Trede, Markauskaite, McEwen, & Macfarlane, 2019; Vukicevic, Djapan, Stefanovic, & Macuzic, 2019; Zhang, Chi, Yang, Nepal, & Moon, 2017). Through the promotion of safety knowledge among the employees, the organizations focus on the practical approach of this knowledge and enhance participation of the employees in safety measurements. Through the safety culture at enterprises, the employees learn about the hazards that they may come in contact with and the possible ways to reduce such hazards (C. A. Mather, Gale, & Cummings, 2017; Reyes, Ellis, Yoder, & Keifer, 2016; Trede et al., 2017). The work related accidents increased in the past and that is why the need to have proper safety guidelines at the industries increased. This resulted in the development of safety practices and regulations that must be practiced at the workplace (Bastan, Azizi, Groesser, & Sheikahmadi, 2018; Coetzee, 2019; Zhao, McCoy, Kleiner, & Feng, 2016). For increasing safety culture practices at the workplace, the effective management of the safety culture knowledge must be ensured (Hejduk & Karwowski, 2016; C. Mather & Cummings, 2017; Rashid, 2017; Sharman, 2016). Through the safety culture practices at the workplace, the employees can best practice these knowledge and this causes the enhancement of the organizational performance and thus, create values (Dimond, Bullock, Lovatt, & Stacey, 2016; El-Sherif & Lahera, 2018; Otto, McMahill, Finley,

Green, & Ward, 2018). The use of mobile technologies is equally important for the effective management of safety practices and thus, influencing the safety at the workplace. With time the use of mobile technology has increased in a number of aspects and so does the safety at the workplace (Bustillo & Mateo, 2020; Horton, Cameron, Devaraj, Hanson, & Hajkowicz, 2018).

Figure 1: Wellbeing services offered by the employer.

Well-being of employees	Percentage offered by the employers
Employee assistance program	30%
Health monitoring	24%
Reimbursement for well-being expenses	26%
Designated office space	27%

Source: (Deloitte)

Figure 2: Top 5 injuries at workplace.

Source: (Connecteam)

The objectives of the study are:

- 1 To determine the impact of safety culture behavior aspects on the safety at work.
- 2 To determine the impact of safety culture psychological aspects on the safety at work.
- 3 To determine the impact of use of mobile technology on the safety at work.
- 4 To determine the impact of the safety at work on the employee well-being.

There is a need to have empirical evidence that can contribute in the theoretical information about the safety culture practices at work and the safety performance of the industries. Therefore, this study will focus on the safety culture aspects that have been practiced in the industrial sector of Thailand. The best practices of safety culture helps in improving the safety

performance of the firm and in reducing the incidents, injuries and accidents at the workplace. Moreover, the present study also focused on the safety culture practices at the workplace in terms of the employees and participation from them. Previous literature studies focused on the safety practices that must be implemented by the administration and the governmental organizations but not on the practical practices of the employees. Therefore, the study will focus on the employee's perspective of the safety culture and the use of mobile technology that will affect the safety practices ta the workplace.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The relationship between the safety culture aspects and practices at the workplace and the well-being of the employees can be best understood with the “ABC theory of safety”. According to this theory, one of the most important determinants of the safety practice at the workplace is the behavior of the employee at the workplace regarding the safety practices (Cox & Jones, 2006; Guldenmund, 2000). This theory also states that for the successful implementation of any of the management practices, the attitude and commitment of the employees is very important. Especially for the efficient environmental management systems and safety practices ta the workplace, the sole focus could not be on the compliance but rather it must be on the culture of the organization (Jianhua & Xiaoyan, 2014; Xie & Guo, 2018). One of the focus aspects of this theory is that, the message regarding the safety practices must be simple as ABC so it would be easy for the employees to understand it, if it is too difficult and over-complicated, the employees would not get it and practice it.

2.1 The impact of safety culture behavior aspects on the safety at work

The attitude and behavior of the employees is very important for the implementation and effective management of the safety culture. According to the research studies(Bernal, Colombo, Al Ai Baky, & Casalegno, 2017; Lanzotti et al., 2018; Williams & Cendón, 2019), the safety culture was introduced as a result of the increased number of workplace accidents that happened in past and thus, the new developed safety standards focused on the behavior of the employees towards the safety culture along with the regulations and practices that must be carried out and practiced by the organizations (Abniki, Bastan, Kasiralvalad, & Ahmadvand, 2017; Ciaccio, Del Cimmuto, & La Torre, 2017; Lorenzini, Oelke, Marck, & Dall'agnol, 2017; Rubin, Giacomini, Allen, Turner, & Kelly, 2020). The emotional reaction of the employees towards the things determines the outcomes and same is the case with the safety culture. If the employees perceive the safety culture as a positive thing for themselves, they will surely be more engaged in these practices and will take care of the safety at the workplace. Thus, the following hypothesis has been generated from the literature studies:

H1: There is a significant relationship between the safety culture behavior aspects and the safety at work.

2.2 The impact of safety culture psychological aspects on the safety at work

Along with the behavior of the employees towards the safety culture, their psychological aspects must also be considered (Ciaccio et al., 2017; Corrigan, Kay, Ryan, Ward, & Brazil, 2019; Lorenzini et al., 2017; Rubin et al., 2020). The psychological dimensions have a most significant impact on the safety practice at work and that is why it has always been the most frequently examined thing in the workplace safety studies. This shows the perception of people towards the safety practices and therefore (Abniki et al., 2017; Bernal et al., 2017; Lanzotti et al., 2018; Williams & Cendón, 2019), the efficient management of the safety standards. Thus, the following hypothesis has been generated from the literature studies:

H2: There is a significant relationship between the safety culture psychological aspects and the safety at work.

2.3 The impact of use of mobile technology on the safety at work

The use of mobile technology has been in case in the last few years and this is because of the wide applications available to ease the work. Literature studies (Bustillo & Mateo, 2020; Dimond et al., 2016; El-Sherif & Lahera, 2018; Horton et al., 2018) shows that the wide implementation of the mobile technology at the workplace has resulted in improvements in the safety at work. As it makes it accessible for the employees to learn about the safety practices and also makes it easy for the management team to reach out every employee (Hejduk & Karwowski, 2016; C. Mather & Cummings, 2017; Otto et al., 2018; Rashid, 2017) and ensure that the employees work according to the standard safety practices by regularly providing them information regarding the safety practices. Thus, the following hypothesis has been generated from the literature studies:

H3: There is a significant relationship between the mobile technology and the safety at work.

2.4 The impact of the safety at work on the employee well-being

Employee well-being must be one of the top priorities of the organizations, as it affects the overall functioning of the organization and work performance of the employees. Literature studies (C. A. Mather et al., 2017; Reyes et al., 2016; Trede et al., 2017; Trede et al., 2019; Vukicevic et al., 2019) have shown the positive and more constructive results from the use of safety practices at the work on the well-being of the employees (Bastan et al., 2018; Coetzee, 2019; Sharman, 2016; Zhao et al., 2016). It has also been observed that the organizations that increase the implementation of the safety culture causes the employees to feel safe at work and thus, increasing the employee well-being. Thus, the following hypothesis has been generated from the literature studies:

H1: There is a significant relationship between the safety at work and the employee well-being.

2.5 Theoretical model

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Approach and Data Collection

It has been observed that in the past studies, the method that has been widely used for the purpose of finding out different aspects of ergonomics and safety in different organizations, the structural equation modelling has been used. Therefore, based on these observations, the researcher has also applied the structural equation modelling technique in order to find out the impact of certain variables on each other in the study. For this purpose, a questionnaire has been developed by the researcher, which will be measured on the basis of five point Likert scale starting from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The questionnaire was developed carefully in a well sequenced way. The language and the content used in the questionnaire were according to the knowledge and information of the sample selected by the author. The questionnaire was distributed among the employees of different herbal companies of Thailand. These employees are selected based on their work in different sectors of the work such as some manufacturing work related to physical and cognitive factors.

3.2 Measurement

The variables that are under study in this research include behavior aspects of safety culture, psychological aspects of safety culture, use of mobile technology, safety at work and employee well-being. All these variables and their constructs have been measured by related items that have been developed and taken from the studies conducted in the past. The first one is employee well-being, which is the dependent variable and has been measured by different items, taken

from the past studies (Holman, 2004). In the similar way, “behavior aspects of safety culture” is an independent variable and it has been measured by eight measurement items that have been taken from the past study (Mohamed, 2003). One of these measurement items is “Sometimes I use machines, devices, or tools whose technical condition may endanger my personal safety”. In the similar way, “psychological aspects of safety culture” is another independent variable, measured by six measurement items taken from the past studies and one of these items is “Employees with extensive experience do not have to comply with health and safety rules” (Mohamed, 2003). Use of mobile technology is the last independent variable of this study and measured by six items, developed by the past studies (Brown, 2002). One of these items is “In the event of a breakdown or accident, I look for information about their causes on the Internet using my smart phone”. In the last we have one mediating variable in the study too, named as safety at work. This variable construct has been measured by six items, taken from the studies conducted in the past in the similar context (Neal & Griffin, 2004). One of these items is “I always follow the procedures for dealing with machine breakdowns or safety hazards”. In this way all the variables and their constructs are measured by using their particularly related items.

3.3 Statistical Analysis

The researcher has effectively analyzed the data previously collected, by using the SPSS and AMOS for obtaining demographic analysis, descriptive analysis, factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis and structure equation modelling.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Demographics

According to the demographics of the study, it has been evident that the data was collected from 450 employees of herbal companies. 248 of them were males and 202 were females in these respondents. Moreover, the respondents having age less than 25 years are 142, those having age from 25 to 35 years are 193, those having 35 to 45 years are 99 while those having age more than 45 years are just 16. The experience of these respondents in the firms has also been observed and it has been found out that most of the respondents are having the experience from 2 to 8 years in the firms.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The results of descriptive statistics presented in the table 1 show that the skewness of the variables is between -1 and +1 which is considered to be the threshold range and also indicates the normality of data. On the other hand, the minimum and maximum values ranging from 1 to 5 shows that there are no outliers in the collected data and data is ready to move in further research process.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
SafWork	450	1.00	5.00	3.1867	1.04837	-.156	.115
EmpWellb	450	1.00	5.00	3.3435	1.01510	-.339	.115
UseOfMT	450	1.00	5.00	3.5010	1.17208	-.524	.115
SafCBA	450	1.00	5.28	3.4084	1.15420	-.499	.115
SCPA	450	1.00	5.00	3.5481	1.15434	-.547	.115
Valid N (listwise)	450						

4.3 KMO and Bartlett's Test

As it can be seen in the table that the value of KMO test is very close to 1.00, this is an important indication that the factor analysis of the variables is beneficial for the results and in the similar way, as the value of the other test i.e. Bartlett's test is less than 0.05, which is an indication that points towards the usefulness of factor analysis in the study.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.949
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	16685.586
	df	435
	Sig.	.000

4.4 Rotated Component Matrix

As per the results of rotated component matrix, it can be evidently seen that all the values of loading for various indicators used by the researcher are greater than 0.7. This can be deduced from the results that the data is eligible for use in the current study and no cross loading in the indicators has been observed.

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
SW1				.817	
SW2				.860	
SW3				.817	
SW4				.763	
SW5				.807	
SW6				.833	
WB1	.718				
WB2	.696				
WB3	.762				
WB4	.824				
WB5	.794				
WB6	.845				
WB7	.894				
WB8	.881				
WB9	.888				
MT1		.834			
MT2		.848			
MT3		.841			
MT4		.881			
MT5		.902			
MT6		.889			
BA1					.833
BA2					.851
BA3					.839
PA1			.805		
PA2			.835		
PA3			.869		
PA4			.862		
PA5			.858		
PA6			.872		

4.5 Convergent and Discriminant Validity

According to the results of convergent and discriminant validity, it can be observed that CR value is greater than 70% while AVE values for all the variables is more than 50%. Moreover, it can also be observed that the loadings of the variables are not related to each other thus indicating that the data is valid to be used in the study.

Table 4: Convergent and Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	BA	SW	WB	MT	PA
BA	0.928	0.812	0.301	0.931	0.901				
SW	0.944	0.737	0.220	0.969	0.469	0.859			
WB	0.950	0.683	0.210	0.995	0.417	0.458	0.826		
MT	0.910	0.844	0.301	0.996	0.549	0.467	0.432	0.919	
PA	0.957	0.787	0.203	0.997	0.368	0.447	0.424	0.450	0.887

4.6 Confirmatory Factors Analysis

It has been clearly evident in the table 5 that the values for all the indicators for confirmatory factor analysis are within the appropriate range that can be seen in the table. These values indicate that the hypothetical model constructed by the researcher is completely fit to be used in the study(Hassan, Hameed, Basheer, & Ali, 2020; Iqbal & Hameed, 2020).

Table 5: Confirmatory Factors Analysis

Indicators	Threshold range	Current values
CMIN/DF	Less or equal 3	2.300
GFI	Equal or greater .80	.826
CFI	Equal or greater .90	.942
IFI	Equal or greater .90	.942
RMSEA	Less or equal .08	.072

Figure 2: CFA

4.7 Structural Equation Modeling

The results of the most important and concluding test i.e. SEM have been presented in table 6. In the table it can be seen that the impact of the independent variables i.e. safety culture psychological aspects and use of mobile technology on employee well being is significant. But the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects has not been found as significant. In the similar way, the mediating impact of safety at work is significant in all cases i.e. between the relationship between all independent and dependent variables.

Table 6: Structural Equation Modeling

Total Effect	Use Of MT	SCPA	Saf CBA	Saf Work
Saf Work	.230**	.235**	.231**	.000
Emp Wellb	.228**	.334***	.149**	.355***
Direct Effect	Use Of MT	SCPA	Saf CBA	Saf Work
Saf Work	.230**	.235**	.231**	.000
Emp Wellb	.146**	.250**	.067	.355**
Indirect Effect	Use Of MT	SCPA	Saf CBA	Saf Work
Saf Work	.000	.000	.000	.000
Emp Wellb	.082**	.083**	.082**	.000

Figure 3: SEM

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Discussion

The basic objective of the study was to find out the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects, safety culture psychological aspects and use of mobile technology on employee well-being in the mediating role of safety at work. The first hypothesis that the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects on employee well-being is significant has been rejected, in accordance with the similar studies in the past (van Nunen, Li, Reniers, & Ponnet, 2018). The next hypothesis that the impact of safety culture psychological aspects on employee well-being is significant has been accepted and this is in line with the results presented in the past studies (Stemn, Bofinger, Cliff, & Hassall, 2019). The next hypothesis that the impact of use of mobile technology on employee wellbeing is significant has been accepted and this is in concordance with the past studies (do Carmo Alonso, Gallier, & Mercado, 2018). The next hypothesis was that the mediating impact of safety at work between safety culture behavioral aspects and employee well-being is significant has been accepted, in accordance with the similar studies in the past (Antonsen, Nilsen, & Almklov, 2017). The next hypothesis was that the mediating impact of safety at work between safety culture psychological aspects and employee well-being is significant has been accepted, and such results have also been found in studies in the past (Bakker & Demerouti, 2018). The last hypothesis was that there is significant mediating impact of safety at work between use of mobile technology and employee well-being has been accepted, in accordance with the similar studies in the past (Guest, 2017).

5.2 Conclusion

Safety measures are very important for any organization so that the employees of the organization feel secured and contented with their jobs. The basic objective of the study was to find out the impact of safety culture behavioral aspects, safety culture psychological aspects and use of mobile technology on employee well-being in the mediating role of safety at work. The results shown that impact of all independent variables, except safety culture behavioral aspects, on employee well-being is significant. In the similar way, it has been found out that

the mediating impact of safety at work has been significant between all the independent and dependent variables of the study.

5.3 Implications

The current study may assist the other researchers get enough information about the safety aspects and other factors related to employee well-being in their studies. In addition, it may provide guidance to the different companies to implement safety culture so that the employee well-being can be ensured. In addition, the policy makers may also get assistance from this study while making policies and regulations in the similar context.

5.4 Limitations and Future Research Indications

The sample size of the study was small and must be increased in the future studies. Moreover, other countries may also be considered other than Thailand while conducting studies of the similar context. Other variables may also be considered along with the variables of the current study so that more knowledge and information can be generated on the relevant topics.

REFERENCES

- Abniki, H., Bastan, M., Kasiralvalad, E., & Ahmadvand, A. (2017). Impacts of Safety Performance and Culture on Work-Related Accidents: A System Dynamics Model. Paper presented at the the 7th International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management (IEOM).
- Antonsen, S., Nilsen, M., & Almklov, P. G. (2017). Regulating the intangible. Searching for safety culture in the Norwegian petroleum industry. *Safety science*, 92, 232-240.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2018). Multiple levels in job demands-resources theory: Implications for employee well-being and performance. *Handbook of well-being*.
- Bastan, M., Azizi, L., Groesser, S., & Sheikahmadi, F. (2018). Analysis of development policies in occupational health and safety management system: a system dynamics approach. Paper presented at the The 2nd IEOM European international conference on industrial engineering and operations management, Paris, France.
- Bernal, G., Colombo, S., Al Ai Baky, M., & Casalegno, F. (2017). Safety++ Designing IoT and Wearable Systems for Industrial Safety through a User Centered Design Approach. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on PErvasive Technologies Related to Assistive Environments.
- Berumen-Flucker, B., Rodriguez, A., Cienega, L., Casanova, V., Pompeii, L., Gimeno Ruiz de Porras, D., & Douphrate, D. I. (2019). Evaluation of safety management and leadership training using mobile technologies among logging supervisors. *Journal of agromedicine*, 24(2), 197-204.
- Brown, B. (2002). Studying the use of mobile technology *Wireless world* (pp. 3-15): Springer.
- Bustillo, J. C. M., & Mateo, J. T. I. (2020). Automated Incident Reporting Management System Using Mobile Technology. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 11(1).
- Charalambous, A., & Kelly, D. (2018). Promoting a safety culture through effective nursing leadership in cancer care. *European Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 36, vi-vii.
- Ciaccio, D., Del Cimmuto, A., & La Torre, G. (2017). Prevedil—the development of a mobile application for the prevention of workplace injury. *Senses and Sciences*, 4(4).
- Coetzee, M. (2019). Organisational Climate Conditions of Psychological Safety as Thriving Mechanism in Digital Workspaces Thriving in Digital Workspaces (pp. 311-327): Springer.

- Corrigan, S., Kay, A., Ryan, M., Ward, M., & Brazil, B. (2019). Human factors and safety culture: Challenges and opportunities for the port environment. *Safety Science*, 119, 252-265.
- Cox, S., & Jones, B. (2006). Behavioural Safety and Accident Prevention: Short-Term 'Fad' or Sustainable 'Fix'? *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 84(3), 164-170. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1205/psep.05186>
- Dimond, R., Bullock, A., Lovatt, J., & Stacey, M. (2016). Mobile learning devices in the workplace: 'as much a part of the junior doctors' kit as a stethoscope'? *BMC medical education*, 16(1), 207.
- do Carmo Alonso, C. M., Gallier, U., & Mercado, M. P. (2018). Improvement of Safety Culture in Industry: A Systematic Review. Paper presented at the Advances in Safety Management and Human Factors: Proceedings of the AHFE 2018 International Conference on Safety Management and Human Factors, July 21-25, 2018, Loews Sapphire Falls Resort at Universal Studios, Orlando, Florida, USA.
- El-Sherif, N., & Lahera, J. R. (2018). Improving safety culture among non-electrical workers. Paper presented at the 2018 IEEE IAS Electrical Safety Workshop (ESW).
- Guest, D. E. (2017). Human resource management and employee well-being: Towards a new analytic framework. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 27(1), 22-38.
- Guldenmund, F. W. (2000). The nature of safety culture: a review of theory and research. *Safety Science*, 34(1), 215-257. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535\(00\)00014-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-7535(00)00014-X)
- Hassan, S. G., Hameed, W. U., Basheer, M. F., & Ali, J. (2020). ZAKAT COMPLIANCE INTENTION AMONG SELF-EMPLOYED PEOPLE: EVIDENCE FROM PUNJAB, PAKISTAN. *AL-ADWAH*, 34(2), 80-96.
- Hejduk, I., & Karwowski, W. (2016). A Knowledge Management Framework of the Information Technology-Based Approach for Improving Occupational Safety Training of Young Workers. *Chinese Business Review*, 15(1), 42-47.
- Holman, D. (2004). Employee well-being in call centres *Call centres and human resource management* (pp. 223-244): Springer.
- Horton, J., Cameron, A., Devaraj, D., Hanson, R., & Hajkowicz, S. (2018). Workplace Safety Futures: The impact of emerging technologies and platforms on work health and safety and workers' compensation over the next 20 years: CSIRO, Canberra.
- Iqbal, J., & Hameed, W. U. (2020). Open Innovation Challenges and Coopetition-Based Open-Innovation Empirical Evidence From Malaysia *Innovative Management and Business Practices in Asia* (pp. 144-166): IGI Global.
- Jianhua, L., & Xiaoyan, S. (2014). Countermeasures of Mine Safety Management based on Behavior Safety Mode. *Procedia Engineering*, 84, 144-150. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.10.420>
- Lanzotti, A., Tarallo, A., Carbone, F., Coccorese, D., D'Angelo, R., Di Gironimo, G., . . . Papa, S. (2018). Interactive tools for safety 4.0: virtual ergonomics and serious games in tower automotive. Paper presented at the Congress of the International Ergonomics Association.
- Lorenzini, E., Oelke, N. D., Marck, P. B., & Dall'agnol, C. M. (2017). Researching safety culture: deliberative dialogue with a restorative lens. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 29(5), 745-749.
- Mather, C., & Cummings, E. (2017). Moving Past Exploration and Adoption: Considering Priorities for Implementing Mobile Learning by Nurses. Paper presented at the CSHI.
- Mather, C. A., Gale, F., & Cummings, E. A. (2017). Governing mobile technology use for continuing professional development in the Australian nursing profession. *BMC nursing*, 16(1), 17.
- Mohamed, S. (2003). Scorecard approach to benchmarking organizational safety culture in construction. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 129(1), 80-88.

- Neal, A., & Griffin, M. A. (2004). Safety climate and safety at work.
- Otto, J., McMahon, A., Finley, K., Green, K., & Ward, N. (2018). Guidance to Promote Workplace Policies and Family Rules to Reduce Cell Phone Use While Driving and Promote Engaged Driving.
- Rashid, K. M. (2017). Coupling Mobile Technology, Position Data Mining, and Attitude toward Risk to Improve Construction Site Safety.
- Reyes, I., Ellis, T., Yoder, A., & Keifer, M. C. (2016). An evaluation tool for agricultural health and safety mobile applications. *Journal of agromedicine*, 21(4), 301-309.
- Rubin, M., Giacomini, A., Allen, R., Turner, R., & Kelly, B. (2020). Identifying safety culture and safety climate variables that predict reported risk-taking among Australian coal miners: An exploratory longitudinal study. *Safety Science*, 123, 104564.
- Sharman, A. (2016). *From accidents to zero: A practical guide to improving your workplace safety culture*: Routledge.
- Stemn, E., Bofinger, C., Cliff, D., & Hassall, M. E. (2019). Examining the relationship between safety culture maturity and safety performance of the mining industry. *Safety science*, 113, 345-355.
- Trede, F., Goodyear, P., Macfarlane, S., Markauskaite, L., McEwen, C., & Tayebjee, F. (2017). Learning in Hybrid Spaces: Designing a Mobile Technology Capacity Building Framework for Workplace Learning', *Work-Integrated Learning in the 21st Century (International Perspectives on Education and Society, Volume 32)*: Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Trede, F., Markauskaite, L., McEwen, C., & Macfarlane, S. (2019). *Education for Practice in a Hybrid Space: Enhancing Professional Learning with Mobile Technology*: Springer.
- van Nunen, K., Li, J., Reniers, G., & Ponnet, K. (2018). Bibliometric analysis of safety culture research. *Safety science*, 108, 248-258.
- Vukicevic, A. M., DJapan, M., Stefanovic, M., & Macuzic, I. (2019). Safe-Tag mobile: A novel javascript framework for real-time management of unsafe conditions and unsafe acts in SMEs. *Safety Science*, 120, 507-516.
- Williams, P., & Cendón, B. V. (2019). Mobile technology and everyday living: case study of the impact of mobile devices on people with learning disabilities in Brazil. *International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing*, 8(4), 167-176.
- Xie, X., & Guo, D. (2018). Human factors risk assessment and management: Process safety in engineering. *Process Safety and Environmental Protection*, 113, 467-482. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psep.2017.11.018>
- Zhang, H., Chi, S., Yang, J., Nepal, M., & Moon, S. (2017). Development of a safety inspection framework on construction sites using mobile computing. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 33(3), 04016048.
- Zhao, D., McCoy, A., Kleiner, B., & Feng, Y. (2016). Integrating safety culture into OSH risk mitigation: a pilot study on the electrical safety. *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management*, 22(6), 800-807.
- <https://connecteam.com/workplace-safety-tips-manufacturing/>
- <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/focus/human-capital-trends/2018/employee-well-being-programs.html>